

Towards an Innovative Framework for Teaching Electron Configuration in Chemistry Courses Using Analogies

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Abstract

This paper explores the possibility of using a simple analogy based on a city with numbered streets and houses with features as a teaching strategy for electron configuration in chemistry courses. The analogy was designed to provide students with an easily understandable framework to help them understand the distribution of electrons within atoms. In this analogy, each numbered street represents an energy level, while the houses on the streets symbolize different types of energy sublevels. The rooms in the houses are associated with orbitals. The hierarchical structure of streets and houses facilitated the distinction between energy levels, energy sublevels, and orbitals. The results of using this analogy were very positive. A significant improvement was observed in the students' ability to write the electron configurations of various chemical elements and to distinguish between energy levels, sublevels, and orbitals. The analogy was successful in clarifying concepts that can be complex or confusing, providing students with clarity and confidence in understanding electron configuration. Specifically, this paper highlights the effectiveness of using a simple analogy as a pedagogical tool to improve learning outcomes in teaching this chemistry topic.

Keywords: Analogy; Educational Innovation; Electron Configuration; Higher Education

1 Introduction

As a fundamental concept in chemistry, electron configuration is the cornerstone for understanding several other topics in the field (Brown & May 2004). It is a central aspect of the general chemistry curriculum from the early stages of education in middle school to advanced courses in professional education (Russell & Larena, 1987). Although initially abstract and perhaps daunting to students, mastery of electron configuration is essential for delving into more complex topics within chemistry (Chang, 2002). Therefore, finding appropriate teaching strategies to help students understand this topic and write the electron configuration of a given chemical element can be helpful in both theoretical and laboratory courses to facilitate their learning (Ramirez, 2017).

Understanding electron configuration lays the groundwork for comprehending the structure and behavior of atoms, forming the basis for exploring the periodic table of elements (Eichinger, 1968). The arrangement of electrons in different energy levels and sublevels directly correlates with an element's position in the periodic table and its chemical properties. For example, the periodic trends in atomic size, ionization energy, and electron affinity can be explained by variations in electron configuration across periods and down groups (Kurushkin, 2015).

Moreover, electron configuration is not a standalone concept, but it's intimately linked to the formation of chemical bonds (Brown & May, 2004). As we delve into the topic, we'll see that knowledge of electron configuration is crucial for understanding how atoms interact to form molecules through ionic bonding, covalent bonding, and metallic bonding (Chang, 2002). The sharing or transfer of electrons between atoms, which underlies these bonding types, can be rationalized by considering the stability achieved through achieving noble gas electron configurations.

Furthermore, electron configuration plays a pivotal role in understanding hybridization, particularly in molecular theory and bonding (Kurushkin, 2015). Hybridization involves mixing atomic orbitals to form new hybrid orbitals, which in turn influences the geometry and bonding properties of molecules. By understanding the electron configuration of the atoms involved, students can more accurately predict the hybridization schemes and molecular shapes.

Since electron configuration is a foundational concept in chemistry education, it has far-reaching implications for understanding the behavior of atoms, the periodic table, chemical bonding, and molecular structure (Ramírez, 2017). By employing effective teaching strategies that cater to diverse learning styles and incorporating practical applications, educators can empower students to master this essential topic and pave the way for further exploration in chemistry (Orgill & Bodner, 2004). Using analogies in teaching specific chemistry topics, such as electron configuration, can be a very effective teaching strategy that facilitates understanding (Thiele & Treagust, 1992).

2 Background

Due to its abstract nature, teaching chemistry, particularly the concept of electron configuration, is often challenging for both teachers and students (Orgill & Bodner, 2004). Analogies are powerful tools for simplifying complex concepts by drawing parallels to familiar phenomena (Huependo, 2021). This abstract examines the effectiveness of analogies in teaching electron configuration in chemistry education.

Electron configuration is a notation used to describe the arrangement of electrons in an atom's electron shells (Brown & May, 2004). It's typically written as a series of numbers and letters representing the energy levels and sublevels where electrons are found (Russell & Larena, 1987).

The electron configuration of an atom is typically represented using a notation that indicates the number of electrons in each energy level and sublevel (Kurushkin, 2015). The main energy levels are often labeled with principal quantum numbers ($n = 1, 2, 3$, etc.), which represent the energy of the electrons. Each level contains one or more sublevels, containing orbitals. These orbitals have different shapes and orientations in space, as described by the angular momentum quantum number (l), which determines the shape of the orbital, the magnetic quantum number (m), which determines the direction the orbital faces, and the spin quantum number (s), which represents the spin of the electron (Chang, 2002).

The electron configuration notation follows a specific format. It begins with the principal quantum number (n), followed by the sublevel designation (s, p, d, f), and the number of electrons in that sublevel (Eichinger, 1968). For example, the electron configuration of hydrogen (H) is $1s^1$, indicating that it has one electron occupying the $1s$ orbital. Helium (He) has an electron configuration of $1s^2$, as it has two electrons filling the $1s$ orbital. Let's take another example, carbon (C), which has an electron configuration of $1s^2 2s^2 2p^2$. This means that carbon has two electrons in the $1s$ orbital, two in the $2s$ orbital, and two in the $2p$ orbital (Brown & May, 2004).

As the atomic number increases, more electrons are added to the atom, filling the available orbitals according to certain rules. The Aufbau principle states that electrons fill the lowest energy orbitals first before moving to higher energy levels (Chang, 2002). This means that the $1s$ orbital is filled before the $2s$ orbital, and so on. Hund's rule dictates that within a sublevel, electrons will occupy individual orbitals with parallel spins before pairing up. This is why, for example, the $2p$ orbital is filled with one electron in each of the three orbitals before any of them pair up (Kurushkin, 2015). The Pauli exclusion principle states that no two electrons in an atom can have the same set of quantum numbers, meaning each orbital can hold a maximum of two electrons with opposite spins. This is why, for example, the $1s$ orbital can hold a maximum of two electrons, one with spin up and one with spin down (Eichinger, 1968).

The periodic table, a powerful tool in chemistry, doesn't just organize elements based on their atomic number, which corresponds to the number of protons in the nucleus (Russell & Larena, 1987). It's a guide that helps us understand electron configurations (Brown & May, 2004). Elements within the same group or column of the periodic table often have similar electron configurations due to their similar chemical properties. By understanding the periodic table and its relationship to electron configurations, you can navigate the world of chemistry with confidence (Huependo, 2021).

Understanding electron configuration is not just a theoretical concept, but it has profound practical applications in predicting an element's chemical behavior (Chang, 2002). This knowledge is not just crucial, but it's the key to understanding how elements interact with each other, including their ability to form bonds with other atoms and molecules (Ramírez, 2017). Furthermore, it's the foundation that helps explain the periodic trends observed in the properties of elements across the periodic table. In essence, electron configuration is a fundamental concept in chemistry, providing valuable insights into the structure and behavior of atoms, and its understanding is key to mastering the subject (Brown & May, 2004).

2.1 Analogies

Analogies are employed as cognitive bridges, connecting unfamiliar concepts with familiar ones (Orgill & Bodner, 2004). In the context of electron configuration, which involves understanding the distribution of electrons within atomic orbitals, analogies can aid in visualizing abstract concepts (Thiele & Treagust, 1992). For instance, the planetary model analogy compares electrons orbiting the nucleus to planets orbiting the sun. This analogy simplifies understanding electron distribution by likening it to familiar celestial motions (Huependo, 2021).

Furthermore, the shell and subshell analogy break down electron configuration into hierarchical levels, akin to the organization of nested Russian dolls. Each shell corresponds to a different energy level, while subshells represent distinct orbital types within each shell (Kurushkin, 2015). This analogy facilitates the comprehension of electron distribution patterns within atoms by providing a tangible framework (Brown & May, 2004).

Moreover, analogies aid in comprehension and foster engagement and retention among learners (Orgill & Bodner, 2004). Analogies capture learners' interest and stimulate their curiosity by tapping into familiar contexts (Huependo, 2021). For instance, the "building blocks" analogy likens electrons to construction workers filling energy levels analogous to floors in a building. This analogy not only elucidates the concept of electron distribution but also instills a sense of ownership in learners as they construct mental models of atomic structure (Thiele & Treagust, 1992).

Additionally, analogies can be tailored to address learners' misconceptions or challenges (Ramírez, 2017). For example, the "bus analogy" addresses the misconception of electrons occupying discrete orbits by likening them to passengers boarding a bus. Electrons can occupy any available seat (orbital) within a particular energy level but cannot exist between seats (orbitals). This analogy clarifies the probabilistic nature of electron distribution, dispelling common misconceptions (Huependo, 2021).

Furthermore, analogies can be adapted to suit diverse learning styles and preferences, demonstrating the inclusivity and considerateness of the teaching approach (Orgill & Bodner, 2004). Visual learners may benefit from spatial analogies such as the "spiral staircase" model, which illustrates the arrangement of electron orbitals in three-dimensional space (Kurushkin, 2015). Auditory learners may find resonance in musical analogies, where electron orbitals are likened to harmonic frequencies within an atomic orchestra (Brown & May, 2004).

In conclusion, analogies are valuable tools for elucidating complex concepts such as electron configuration in chemistry education. By leveraging familiar contexts and visual metaphors, analogies facilitate comprehension,

engagement, and retention among learners. Educators are encouraged to harness the power of analogies to demystify abstract concepts and cultivate a deeper understanding of chemistry among students.

3 Methodology

To use an analogy that would help chemistry students understand the topic of electron configuration, they were told to imagine a city whose streets are numbered as in some towns and that as the number of the street would increase, the size of the street would also increase, that is, street 1 < street 2, < street 3, etc.

They were also told that in each street there could only be a number of houses equal to the number of the street, i.e. in street 1 there was only one house, in street 2, two houses, in street 3, three houses and so on. Then they were told that there were only four different types of houses, depending on the number of bedrooms or alcoves inside and all with odd numbers starting from the simplest with one bedroom, then with three, five and seven alcoves.

Representing this schematically, it would look something like this for the first four streets:

Figure 1. City with numbered streets

At this point, it was clarified that each bedroom had two single beds with opposite headboards. This is why each sleeping room could accommodate a maximum of two people if one lay down in one direction and the other in the other direction. However, there could also be only one person or none, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Bedroom in a house on First Street

The students were then asked how many people at most could be in each type of house, to which they all answered quickly, 2, 6, 10, and 14, which was used to try to name them in some appropriate way. They agreed the smallest house was a "simple" house, and that is what it was called; the one with three bedrooms or six people was said to look like a student house of a polytechnic university, so it was called "poly" house, the five-bedroom house was called "decade" house, because of the number of people it could have and the biggest one, which seemed to be made to house a football team, was called "football" house.

It was not difficult for the students to describe that in this city, they could distinguish that there was a simple house on street 1, a simple house and a poly house on street 2, a simple house, a poly house, and a decade house on 3rd Street and finally a simple house, a poly house, a decade house and a football house on 4th Street.

Then they were asked if people were coming to stay in that town, would they indicate by the street number and the type of house where the first, the second, the third would arrive and so on, the students answered that the first person would do it in the simple house on street 1, the second person in the same house and on the same Street, but they were reminded, since they were in the same room, since the simple house only has one, they had to go to bed in opposite directions, something similar happened for the third and fourth person who entered the simple house on 2nd Street, and continued with the fifth person in the poly house on 2nd Street, but when referring to the sixth person they said that he entered the same first bedroom of the poly house on 2nd Street in the opposite direction, at that moment it was clarified to them that since there were still two empty bedrooms in that house simple, the most appropriate thing was for that sixth person, the second to enter the poly house on 2nd Street, to stay in the next room, the seventh person could still do something similar and take a bedroom alone, but already the eighth person would have to share his room with the first person who entered that house, that is, with the fifth person who entered the town and so on. The schematic would look something like this, using arrows to facilitate the representation of people.

Figure 3: 1st to 9th person

In this way, one filled up the houses until the fifteenth person, who arrived at the third bedroom of the poly house on 3rd Street, which appeared as follows:

Figure 4: 1st to 15th person

Next, one told the students that they could avoid drawing the diagram of streets and houses if they only showed how many people there were in a given home and street, always indicating the street number, then the name of the house, and then the number of people in it in this way:

1 simple 2

2 simple 2 2 poly 6

3 simple 2 3 poly 3

After this, one told them that to simplify the writing, one would write only the first letter of each house and that the number of people in them would be written as an exponent like this.

1 s²

2 s² 2p⁶

3s² 3p³

Writing it straight would look like this: 1s² 2s² 2p⁶ 3s² 3p³. One asked the students to do the same from person number 1 to 18 and to indicate in each case how many bedrooms were full, half complete, and empty.

When one noted that the students had understood this whole concept of everyday life, the topic of the structure of the atom began to be discussed, emphasizing that the electrons were distributed outside the nucleus in energy levels that were called levels 1, 2, 3, etc. in which there were energy sublevels, known as s, p, d and f, which in turn contained orbitals, where there could be up to two electrons, as long as they rotated in the opposite direction, the s sublevel only had one orbital and therefore both a maximum of 2 electrons, the p sublevel, three orbitals, that is, a maximum of 6 electrons, the d, five orbitals with a maximum of 10 electrons and the f, seven orbitals with a maximum of 14 electrons. One explained that this representation of the arrangement of electrons in energy levels and sublevels, which an atom had given by its atomic number, was called electron configuration.

4 Results

In the assessment, a substantial portion of students showcased an impressive grasp of the analogy, effectively linking the street number to energy level, type of house to energy sublevel, room to orbital, and electron to person. Moreover, they exhibited comprehension regarding the opposite spins of electrons within orbitals, drawing a parallel with the sleeping positions of individuals in bedrooms.

This pedagogical approach not only facilitated students in constructing electron configurations for various chemical elements but also equipped them with the necessary skills to explore related topics such as quantum numbers, periodic properties, Lewis structures, and chemical bonds.

This instructional strategy's efficacy in elucidating seemingly abstract concepts like electron configuration may stem from its alignment with the constructivist paradigm (Hernandez, 2008), inherent in metacognitive processes. Students actively construct their understanding by establishing connections between familiar analogies and abstract concepts, thereby enhancing metacognitive awareness and knowledge retention.

Nevertheless, a minority subgroup comprising approximately 10 to 12% of students voiced dissent regarding this teaching methodology. They articulated concerns about confusion between the core topic and its analogical representation, advocating for a more direct instructional approach. Some students preferred to abstain from analogies altogether, while others acknowledged their initial comprehension of the city-based analogical model but encountered difficulties during examinations. They lamented the need for questions framed explicitly within the analogical framework, leading to disparities between initial understanding and exam requirements.

These findings underscore the importance of a balanced approach in integrating analogies within pedagogical practices. While analogies can significantly enhance comprehension and engagement for most students, it is crucial to address the concerns of the minority subgroup. Educators should aim for clarity in transitioning between analogical representations and core concepts while carefully incorporating analogies into assessment strategies to align with students' expectations and comprehension levels. This approach can optimize the benefits of analogical teaching while mitigating potential drawbacks for a diverse student population.

5 Conclusions

Using a straightforward analogy, likening the electron configuration to a city or town with numbered streets and houses with one, three, five, and seven rooms has proven to be a remarkably effective teaching strategy.

This approach, which is part of most general chemistry programs, helps to demystify the complex topic of electron configuration. The city analogy strategy, a simple yet powerful tool, compares electron configuration to the structured layout of a bustling city or tranquil town. This straightforward approach, seamlessly integrated into the curricula of most general chemistry programs, serves as a beacon of clarity amidst the labyrinthine complexities inherent in the study of electron configuration.

Whether you're a university scholar, a chemistry enthusiast, or simply someone with a curious mind, the city analogy strategy welcomes you. This strategy, meticulously refined and rigorously tested within the hallowed halls of the Tecnológico de Monterrey, transcends the confines of specific academic institutions. Its universal applicability extends to chemistry courses spanning all academic echelons and, indeed, even to those individuals whose pursuits lie beyond the conventional realms of academia.

The city analogy serves as a resource for understanding electron configuration. It makes it easier for us to see it and understand it. As they walk the streets of this imaginary city and enter the houses, each with its layout of rooms, students embark on a journey of discovery and learning about how electrons are organized within an atom. Some students shared that the city analogy strategy helped them understand the concept of electron configuration in a way that traditional methods could not. This educational strategy facilitates the teaching of electron configuration and explains its basic principles in a clear and simple manner.

The city analogy strategy is not only academically useful, but it also transcends disciplinary boundaries and can capture the imagination of anyone interested in the subject. It's important to note, however, that while the

strategy has proven effective for many, it may not work for everyone. Some students may find it too simplistic or prefer more traditional teaching methods. The city analogy is a testament to the transformative power of innovative pedagogy.

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